

**EFFECTS OF THE SIMPLIFIED PYC READING
APPROACH THROUGH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF
“BASA BAYA LAHAT” PROGRAM TO THE READING
SKILLS DEVELOPMENT OF THE READERS**

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Effects of the Simplified PVC Reading Approach Through the Implementation of “Basa Baya Lahat” Program to the Reading Skills Development of the Readers

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Abstract

Reading is an essential means of gaining knowledge and an instrument for learning. However, the deterioration of the quality of learning is one of the effects of the reading problems that have become a concern, particularly for teachers facing challenges. Numerous reading literacy programs, approaches, and strategies have to be developed to aid struggling learners in facilitating and improving language acquisition. Hence, the researcher conducted a pre-experimental study to determine the effects of the Simplified PVC Reading Approach as a teaching aid to the reading skills development through phonological awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension of struggling readers. This study also explored whether the studied variable has a significant effect or not on the reading level of struggling learners. Eight students who had been identified under the "frustration reading level" in Argao National High School, District of Mogpog, Division of Marinduque, S.Y. 2021-2022 were selected as participants and were subjected to the 15-day implementation of the Basa Baya Lahat (Reading Brigade) program as an enhancement program. Based on the post test conducted after the experiment using the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach and validated reading materials, it was found out that the eight participants significantly increased their reading level to "instructional level" and "independent level". This indicates that the Simplified PVC Reading Approach had significant effects on the improvement of reading skills development at the word recognition level with a mean of 4.425%, at the comprehension level on oral reading with a mean of 21.460%, and the comprehension level on silent reading with a mean of 5.4425%. This implies that the proposed reading approach and the activities performed within the enrichment reading program effectively improved the word recognition and comprehension skills (oral and silent) of students with reading difficulties. Moreover, this could be a working tool and teaching aid for teachers to help struggling readers. As a result, the study's findings also imply that continuously developing theory, approach, and strategies can help address learners' growing reading issues overtime and thus develop their reading skills in the long run.

Keywords: *basa baya lahat(reading brigade) program, frustration level, one- sample t-test, pre-experimental, reading, struggling reader, Simplified PVC reading approach*

Introduction

Reading is a key to the door that unlocks the enlightenment of all knowledge and plays an indispensable role in acquiring knowledge. Reading is one of the essential skills that an individual learner must master. According to Aracelo (1994), referenced by Panerio (2008), "85% of people's activities entail and involve reading." People read directional signage, commercials, restaurant menus, cookbook recipes, pharmaceutical dosages, and other things. It also forms the basis for lifelong learning and is vital to students' academic achievement. When students read, they acquire various essential skills, including decoding sounds to letters, fluency, vocabulary, sentence construction, and working memory and attention. Since reading is a prerequisite for many other disciplines, it serves as a primary avenue to knowledge and a tool for learning for all students who enroll in different courses.

The National Reading Panel (2000) asserts that teaching English language beginners to read is challenging. To read effectively and fluently, students

must combine various cognitive functions, such as word recognition, sentence and text interpretation, and memory retention. Understanding the alphabetic system, including letter-sound correspondences, spelling patterns, and how to use this information in reading, is a crucial part of the learning process for novices. Furthermore, reading proficiency is also necessary for gaining knowledge, understanding oneself, and comprehending the world. The ability of today's pupils to grasp and thoughtfully use a multitude of texts will determine their future. It also depends on their capacity to employ reading abilities to think critically and communicate their ideas both orally and in writing (Department of Education, 2013). Gray and McCutchen (2006) indicate that teaching young learners to read is an essential cornerstone for improving and enhancing educational performance and has far-reaching effects.

However, teachers in the Philippines are most concerned about the vast number of students whose professional prospects or social possibilities may be jeopardized by the insufficient reading abilities required to fulfill the expectations of an increasingly competitive society. In 2018, the Organization for

Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) administered the Programme for International Student Evaluation (PISA), an assessment of 15-year-old students in 79 nations. The Philippines was ranked 70th in reading, with a mean score of 340 and 79th overall, compared to the OECD average of 486. PISA defines reading literacy as "understanding, evaluating, reflecting on, and engaging with texts to attain one's goals, develop one's knowledge and potential, and participate in society." Consequently, the Philippines shared a high proportion of poor performance with all other PISA-participating nations and economies. Thus, 80 percent of Filipino learners did not meet the required competency level in reading. The learner's poor English, mathematics, and science performance can be related to their lack of reading and comprehension skills. In light of this, the Department of Education (DepEd) has created the Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiatives) to enhance its advocacy for reading and to pledge to make every learner at their grade level a proficient reader. The execution of the K-12 Basic Education Program seems to have connected with the relevance of building students' competitive reading skills.

As a result, learning to read presents real hurdles, issues, and problems in the learners' reading abilities that must be addressed. On the other hand, teachers face several challenges because one is responsible for the learning strategy, and the teachers have difficulty teaching reading. If students provide an appropriate plan incorporating engaging activities, they will be more active and aware of the need to learn. With this, numerous reading literacy programs have been developed to aid struggling learners in learning about letters, sounds, and words to facilitate and improve language acquisition. It is then imperative that unskilled and struggling readers have the opportunities to improve.

Research Questions

In light of the above-given information, this study presented a reading approach to help improve the reading skills of struggling readers through an enrichment reading program. The Division of Marinduque initiated and implemented the Basa Baya Lahat program, a reading camp to help struggling readers at Argao National High School. The study aimed to determine whether the proposed Simplified PVC (phonological awareness, vocabulary building, and comprehension skills) reading approach affects students' reading skills.

This study specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the reading level of struggling readers before implementing the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach through the Basa Baya Lahat program?
2. What is the reading level after implementing the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach through the Basa Baya Lahat program?
3. Is there a significant effect on reading level improvement after implementing the Simplified PVC Reading Approach in terms of:
 - 3.1 Miscues; and
 - 3.2 Reading comprehension?
4. What is the implication of the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach for developing the reading skills of struggling readers?

Methodology

This section presents the research design, locale, population and sample, instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study employed a pre-experimental design, in which either a single group of participants or multiple groups of observables followed a hypothesized change-causing intervention or therapy. The researcher utilized a pre-experimental design to investigate the effects of the suggested research-based reading materials on the development of the reading skills of struggling readers. This study determined how the researcher's intervention program would affect the experiment.

As cited by Arikunto (2000), a pre-experimental study aims to determine whether the studied variable has an effect or nothing. Moreover, according to Ary (2010), experimental design is the conceptual framework for an experiment. The most crucial criterion is that the study's design appropriately assesses the particular hypothesis. This study is a one-time case study in which a single group is exposed to a treatment or condition and then measured to determine its effects or the potential to cause change.

As a result, the proposed Simplified PVC (Phonological Awareness, Vocabulary, and

Comprehension) reading approach and contextualized reading materials were used to implement the "*Basa Baya Lahat*" program. This approach helps the reading skills development of struggling readers among junior high school students, allowing the study to ascertain whether there was a significant improvement in the reading levels of struggling readers.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Argao National High School, District of Mogpog, Division of Marinduque, where the *Basa Baya Lahat* Program is being implemented. This school continuously supports the program, where they identify struggling readers every year.

Population and Sample

Before collecting the sample, the researcher needed to identify the population. Sugiyono (2013) explains that population is a geographic generalization with the following characteristics: the object or subject that has the quality and specific characteristics set by the researcher to learn.

The researcher used purposive sampling to get the number of participants. In this research, the purposive sampling technique was utilized to obtain samples. According to Arikunto (2000), purposive sampling is the process of selecting samples by taking subjects that are not based on level or area but are taken based on a specific purpose.

The participants of the study were the identified struggling readers, specifically under "*frustration reading level*" and "*non-readers*", or those characterized by a low level of reading, from Grades 7–10, ages 12–16 years old, based on the consolidated reading assessment report for the school year 2021–2022.

Table 1 shows the number of students under the "frustration level" identified as struggling readers for the school year 2021–2022. These 12 students under the "frustration level" served as participants who were needed to participate in the enhancement reading program.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study by Grade Level*

Grade Level	Level of Reading Population (Frustration Level)	Actual Number of Participants
Grade 7	6	5
Grade 8	3	2
Grade 9	2	1
Grade 10	1	0
Total	12	8

However, due to the constraints of the current pandemic, only eight out of 12 students participated in the Division's *Basa Baya Lahat* Program. Two of them had already transferred to another school, while the other two students could not get consent from their parents for personal reasons.

Research Instrument

Instrument selection is an essential step in carrying out this research. Arikunto (2006) explains that the success of research is determined by the instrument employed since it collects the data required to answer research questions and test the hypotheses gained from the instrument. Additionally, instruments are used to objectively obtain quantitative information on various attributes (Hascher & Hadjar, 2018).

With this, the study's research instrument used a survey questionnaire to gather the pertinent data regarding the identified struggling readers and to thoroughly conduct an experiment utilizing the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach. This proposed approach intends to cater the struggling readers' needs and to contextualize instructional reading materials. The focus of the approach is the three components of reading: phonological awareness, vocabulary development, and comprehension skills, through the implementation of the *Basa Baya Lahat* Program - Culminating Activity in the Division of Marinduque.

In addition, after the contextualized reading approach experiment, a one-sample t-test and the PHIL-IRI assessment tool were used to assess the effects on struggling readers' reading skills development. The following table shows the description of the reading level using the PHIL-IRI standard tool:

Table 2 shows the interpretation and description of the conducted post-test, as prescribed in PHIL-IRI. If the students' word reading score is between 97 and 100%

and their comprehension score is between 80 and 100%, they are considered independent level. However, if the student's word reading score is between 90 and 96% and their comprehension score is 59 to 79%, they are considered to be at the instructional level. If the student's word reading score is 89% and below and their comprehension score is 58% and below, they are at a frustration level.

Table 2. Description of the Reading Level using PHIL-IRI standard tool

Oral & Silent Reading Level	Word Reading Score (in %)	Comprehension Score (in %)
Independent	97-100%	80 -100%
Instructional	90-96%	59-79%
Frustration	89% & below	58% & below

Before administering the research instrument, the researcher needed to establish its validity to ensure its content was valid. In order to effectively use the instructional reading material, the researcher asked for assistance from the three validators: an Associate Professor and Doctor of Reading Instruction; a Master Teacher I and a graduate of Master of Arts in English Language Teaching; and an Instructor and a graduate of Master of Arts in English with a major in IT and Multimedia Arts, who specialized in this field of subject and who fully verified if the materials are ready for floating. The validation tool results in an overall indicator rated as 5, which means "most valid." This means that the instrument appeared valid and could provide unbiased data for the interpretation, allowing a 0-5% error. Also, this means that: a) the instrument fits with the variables under investigation, thus measuring what it intends to measure; b) the instrument can measure items of the variables within a given time frame; and c) the instrument can gather factual data, eliminating bias and subjectivity. With the assessment of the materials based on the responses of the validators, the proposed research instrument is valid and was ready to be used.

Data Gathering Procedure

Table 3 shows the procedures that were followed to acquire the needed data efficiently:

Table 3. Data Collection Procedure

Phases	Date/Duration	Activities	Output
Phase I	May 5 -10, 2022	Drafting of the project.	Approved project proposal
Phase II	May 10 - May 31, 2022	Developing a reading approach and contextualizing reading materials to be used as a proposed strategy for reading. Dissemination of letter to the evaluators;	Validated reading materials
Phase III	June 1-3, 2022	Asking for validation of research instrument	Approved validation tool
Phase IV	July 19 -20, 2022	Seeking permission from the school's division office or the public school district office to conduct research at Argao National High School in the Mogpog District	Approved permit
Phase V	July 21-22, 2022	Gathering of data from the Language Teachers of Argao National High School, learners who are identified as struggling readers	Collected data from the school consolidated report of Grade 7-10 learners through Phil-IRI assessment
Phase VI	July 23, 2022	Home visits to identified struggling readers and distribution of the parent's consent	Approved consent from the parent's participants
Phase VII	July 23-24, 2022	Preparation of the 15-day "Basa Baya Lahat" program as a reading enhancement program	Approved contextualized, and validated reading materials
Phase VIII	July 25, 2022	Pre-reading Assessment	Results of the pre-test before the implementation of the Reading Enhancement Program
Phase IX	July 25 - August 12, 2022	Launching of 15-day Division Reading Program "Basa Baya Lahat Program"	Improvement of the reading ability of the struggling readers. Result of the Post-test after the implementation of the reading enhancement program
Phase X	August 12, 2022	Post-reading Assessment	Implementation of the reading enhancement program
Phase XI	September- October, 2022	Interpretation and tabulation of the data analysis	Interpreted data and findings from the researcher

Data Analysis Procedure

This study followed a pre-experimental procedure employing the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach and contextualized instructional reading

materials for experimentation through the *Basa Baya Lahat* program to see its effects on the reading skills development of the identified struggling readers.

Hatch (2002) defines *data analysis* as "the systematic steps of categorizing data into related themes to explain the meaning of the relationships." depicts the process of conducting and collecting, analysing of data to determine the effects of the proposed reading approach for struggling readers on the development of their reading skills.

This study showed how the data were collected and analyzed. Since the purpose was to find out the reading level of struggling readers in terms of word recognition and comprehension of English texts (oral and silent reading) and its effects to the reading skills through the implementation of the Division *Basa Baya Lahat* Program to the struggling readers of Argao National High School.

After the 15-day experiment using the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach and the reading materials, the researcher administered a post-reading test. The prepared post-reading test comprised 40 items: 20 items for oral reading assessment and 20 items for silent reading assessment. This process focused on three aspects: a) determining miscues; b) determining reading comprehension level in oral and silent reading. In miscue analysis, the researcher used the PHIL IRI Form (see Appendix H) to determine their word recognition reading level. This miscues analysis focused on mispronunciation, omission, substitution, repetition, transposition, and reversal.

In determining comprehension level through oral reading, the researcher administered a test included two passages read orally, followed by comprehension questions. In determining comprehension level through silent reading, the researcher administered a test comprised of two passages followed by comprehension questions (see Appendix H). The researcher also used the PHIL IRI assessment to determine their reading levels.

The researcher made sure that proper experimentation procedures had been followed in collecting data, in-depth analysis, and observation. After the data analysis, interpretation results and conclusions followed.

Ethical Concerns

Language instructors (local implementers) of the "*Basa Baya Lahat*" program in the schools of the

Division of Marinduque participated in this study to investigate the impact of reading skills development on struggling readers. With the conduct of this experiment, numerous precautions were required to guarantee the confidentiality and security of the information submitted by participants. In order to avoid future challenges that may develop throughout the research process, these concerns had been highlighted beforehand. Consent, confidentiality, and data protection were among the significant issues addressed.

In order to minimize confusion during the implementation of the study, experimental procedures and the data collected from the research instrument had been analyzed transparently and straightforwardly. The research participants were asked to review the data carefully and comprehensively to avoid errors and inconsistencies in their responses. They also agreed to sign a waiver ensuring the confidentiality of their names and personal information as well as an assurance that the information they provided would be treated with utmost care. These measures had been taken to foster trust between the researcher and participants.

Results and Discussion

The results and discussions are divided into four sections in accordance with the study's statement of the problem. First, it deals with the data of the conducted reading assessment of the junior high school of Argao National High School before implementing the program. Second, it shows the reading level of the struggling readers after the implementation of the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach through the *Basa Baya Lahat* program. Third, it reveals the significant effects of the improvement using the experimented proposed reading approach and reading materials. Fourth, it explains the implications of the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach through the *Basa Baya Lahat* Program (Reading Brigade) for developing the reading skills of struggling readers.

Before conducting the research, the Department of Education presented programs to affect the reading needs of learners. This program follows DepEd Order No. 45 of 2002, also known as the "*Every Child a Reader Program*," a national program to have every child be a reader by their grade level. Numerous intervention and remediation programs were needed to be conducted by instructors in response to a DepEd

campaign to address the disparity in English reading difficulties. However, there needs to be a specific effective approach offered to teach reading.

In support to this campaign, the researcher developed a model reading approach called the Simplified PVC Reading Approach (see Appendix B), focusing on the foundational phonological awareness skills, vocabulary, and comprehension with its objectives. The model reading approach provides and contextualizes reading materials for reading skill development through an intervention reading program.

This simplified PVC reading approach needs to be experimented with to see its effects on struggling readers. The researcher prepared a set of activities (see Appendix G) aligned with the offered reading approach. During the implementation of the 15-day *Basa Baya Lahat* program, the researcher divided the 15 days into teaching the different reading components. The first five days concentrated on phonological awareness to help struggling readers memorize all the consonant letter names and sounds using the alphabetic principle as the backbone for reading success. This material includes short vowel words in the CVC pattern, consonant blends, and consonant digraphs, long vowel words ending in a silent letter. The next five days concentrated on building vocabulary so that the students can identify the meaning of words through contextual clues and structural analysis. The last five days, on the other hand, concentrated on oral and silent reading comprehension skills to understand the texts. This material included graded reading comprehension passages that address how to get the main ideas, note details, make predictions, sequence events, and support details in a reading text.

The *Basa Baya Lahat* program started on July 25 and ended on August 13, 2022. The enhancement program was completed by eight participants from grades 7 to 10 at Argao National High School.

Reading Level of the Struggling Readers Before the Implementation of the Basa Baya Lahat (Reading Brigade) Using the Proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach

Based on the gathered data from the school's consolidated report of the pre-reading assessment administered at the beginning of the school year 2021-2022 at Argao National High School District of Mogpog, Division of Marinduque through the PHIL-IRI standard tool, 25 students were identified under "frustration level." These students were classified as

struggling readers because they have low reading levels. The teachers provided remediation and intervention to pupils who needed assistance in improving their reading abilities by giving a variety of supplemental activities.

However, before the school year ended, the reading teachers administered a post-reading test to see if the struggling readers under the "frustration level" had improved their reading skills. According to the school's consolidated reading post-test assessment report submitted to the District of Mogpog for School Year 2021-2022, there were still 12 students who are below the "frustration level" and appeared to have not improved on their reading levels. These students needed to participate in the 15-day *Basa Baya Lahat* program the Division of Marinduque initiated to help every struggling reader become independent. However, due to different personal reasons, only eight participants attended the culminating activities.

In support of this finding, a research study by Biancarosa and Snow (2004) reported that over eight million adolescents struggle with reading. According to Lerner (2003), for unknown reasons, some learners cannot use reading to learn and acquire new information, ideas, attitudes, and values beginning in standards four and upward. It is regrettable that even after receiving instruction, 17.5% of students cannot read proficiently at higher class levels.

The table 4 shows the post-test results before implementing the *Basa Baya Lahat* program, which determined the students' reading levels based on word recognition and comprehension skills in both oral and silent reading.

Table 4. *Post-test Results in Word Recognition Determining Miscues and Speed Before the Implementing the Basa Baya Lahat Program*

Student No.	Grade Level	Passage Total Words	Miscues	Total Correct Read	Words per minute	Rating	Word Reading Level
1	Grade 7	160	27	133	21	83.1%	Frustration Level
2	Grade 7	160	36	124	13	77.5%	Frustration Level
3	Grade 7	160	31	129	13	80.6%	Frustration Level
4	Grade 7	160	31	129	13	80.6%	Frustration Level
5	Grade 7	160	38	122	12	76.3%	Frustration Level
6	Grade 8	160	32	128	14	80%	Frustration Level
7	Grade 8	160	34	126	24	78.6%	Frustration Level
8	Grade 9	160	32	128	14	80%	Frustration Level

Table 4.1. *Post-test Results in Reading Comprehension Skills through Oral Reading*

Student	Grade Level	Air Currents Passage 1		The Brain Passage 2		Total Score	Rating %	Reading Level
		Score	No. of Questions	Score	No. of Questions			
1	Grade 7	3	7	3	7	6	42.9%	Frustration Level
2	Grade 7	4	7	3	7	7	50%	Frustration Level
3	Grade 7	3	7	3	7	6	42.9%	Frustration Level
4	Grade 7	2	7	3	7	5	35.7%	Frustration Level
5	Grade 7	5	7	3	7	8	51.1%	Frustration Level
6	Grade 8	2	7	1	7	3	21.4%	Frustration Level
7	Grade 8	4	7	3	7	7	50%	Frustration Level
8	Grade 9	3	7	3	7	6	42.9%	Frustration Level

This shows the results of the post-test conducted last month (May–June 2022) by the reading coordinator of Argao National High School. The eight participants from all grade levels appeared to be at the "frustration level," as their scores were 89% and below.

This study demonstrated that the offered remediation and intervention program was ineffective for other students. Also, this reveals that the eight participants have committed errors in mispronunciation, omission, substitution, and insertion of words and letters while doing the oral reading.

With this, a firm foundation in language ability and word recognition skills is needed to build higher language acquisition skills. That is why the researcher concluded that intensive and explicit teaching of phonological awareness and phonics are necessary foundations for understanding the relationship between letters and spoken sounds, which is included in the proposed Simplified PVC Reading approach and the suggested reading materials.

Table 4.1 shows the results of the post-test conducted by the reading teacher from Argao National High School to assess the reading comprehension level in oral reading before the implementation of the *Basa Baya Lahat* Program.

This study reveals that eight students scored 89% or lower and thus remained below the "frustration level." This study concludes that students can no longer read and understand the text. As a result, teachers must teach and provide various reading materials to assist struggling readers. The need for an effective approach from the reading teacher in the school may aid in tailoring specific materials to contribute to students' learning.

In support to this, Sari (2017) stated that there were still many problems in the learning process of reading comprehension. In the United States (USA), 40% of learners experience significant problems becoming competent readers, and 40% of fourth and eighth graders fail to read at the level considered fundamental for grade-level school work (Hugo et al., 2005).

In addition, Casinillo and Tavera (2020) found out that the elementary reading programs in the Hilongos South District prioritize word recognition, comprehension, and vocabulary acquisition. Unfortunately, reading proficiency remains a perennial problem among teachers, especially now that students are surrounded by high-tech devices, risk factors that reduce students' motivation to read at home and school. The researcher also observed in the reading assessment using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil- IRI) that only 55% of the learners belonged to the independent level and the rest to the frustration level.

With this in mind, it is a daunting task for teachers to decide on the most suitable approach that benefits all learners because relying on one specific approach or set of materials may cause problems. However, this challenges the researcher to come up with an idea to formulate an approach to reading that will help struggling readers become independent. The Simplified PVC Reading Approach aims to develop

and improve the reading skills of struggling readers. This approach specifically caters to the needs of the students through differentiated and interactive activities focusing on increasing comprehension skills (refer to Appendix F).

Table 4.2 reveals the results of a post-test in reading comprehension administered using silent reading to determine their reading level before implementing the *Basa Baya Lahat Program*. It reveals that eight students in all grade levels remained at a "frustration level," as they met the rating of 89% or below, and these students were usually those who cannot comprehend and understand the text. As a result, the Division of Marinduque has chosen the following students who fall under the "frustration level" category to participate in the 15-day *Basa Baya Lahat Program*, which culminates in summer camp activities.

Table 4.2. *Post-test Results in Comprehension Skills through Silent Reading*

Student Level	Grade	Air Currents Passage 1		The Brain Passage 2		Total Score	Rating %	Reading Level
		Score	No. of Questions	Score	No. of Questions			
1	Grade 7	3	7	3	7	6	42.9%	Frustration Level
2	Grade 7	4	7	3	7	7	50%	Frustration Level
3	Grade 7	3	7	3	7	6	42.9%	Frustration Level
4	Grade 7	2	7	3	7	5	35.7%	Frustration Level
5	Grade 7	5	7	3	7	8	51.1%	Frustration Level
6	Grade 8	2	7	1	7	3	21.4%	Frustration Level
7	Grade 8	4	7	3	7	7	50%	Frustration Level
8	Grade 9	3	7	3	7	6	42.9%	Frustration Level

In a similar study to Quimbo (2021), the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) English Post-Test result at Kibacania Elementary School for the school year 2018– 2019 revealed that 24% of the students in grades four to six were frustrated readers. When examined closely by the class advisers through the individual oral reading of graded passages, it was found that the frustrated readers had word recognition problems on words with consonant blends and

consonant digraphs. The result finds that both frustrated and instructional readers had problems with fluency, vocabulary, and reading comprehension. This result reveals and replicates the learners' depressing level of reading proficiency.

According to Luz (2007), the reading proficiency report revealed that 71.19 percent of elementary school graduates in the nation's capital (Metro Manila) fell into the "frustration" or "instructional" reading categories. These results were below the required reading level for students to graduate from elementary school. A similar case that one can consider was the 2003 Self-Assessment Test in English administered to all English, mathematics, and science public secondary school in the United States. This report revealed that only 19% passed with a score of at least 75%. With this in mind, it is equally crucial to analyze the teacher's role when examining this low student performance. This poor reading was a reflection of poor language proficiency, whether in English or the national language.

With this, the researcher proposed Simplified PVC, a new approach to teaching reading that focuses on the foundational skills of reading: phonological awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension, and is guided by Vygotsky's zone of proximal development theory in teaching reading. The researcher also suggested contextualized reading materials adapted from different sources (refer to Appendix F) to employ during the 15-day implementation of the enhancement program.

Therefore, research has demonstrated reading skills' importance for comprehension and academic achievement. When reading skills are inadequate, several issues arise, resulting in learning frustration (Bender et al., 1995). As a result, teachers must carefully plan their approach, strategy, and materials for the enhancement program.

Reading Level of the Struggling Readers After Implementing the *Basa Baya Lahat* (Reading Brigade) Using The Proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach

The proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach was successfully utilized by implementing the *Basa Baya Lahat* program (Reading Brigade) from July 25 to August 12, 2022, to help the eight struggling readers. To easily cater to the needs of the struggling readers, the researcher provided a set of daily activities (refer to Appendix G) aligned with the needs of the learners using a combination of assisted and modeled

approaches to teaching. The activities and worksheets focus on phonological awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension.

After conducting the 15-day experiment using the proposed approach and suggested materials as teaching aids, the researcher administered a post-reading test to the eight participants to measure their reading levels and determine if they had increased and progressed from their previous reading level.

The teacher prepared a validated reading test material for the post-reading test. The students were tasked to read the passage orally in the oral reading test. At the same time, the researcher documented their reading speed and miscues using the Miscue Analysis using the PHIL-IRI tool. This study classified the different miscues into insertion, mispronunciation, omission, repetition, reversal, substitution, and transposition. Hence, the reading comprehension test was employed after the oral reading test. The students read the passages silently and answered the comprehension test.

Based on the gathered data, the following were the results of the post-reading test after employing the Simplified PVC Reading Approach along with the suggested and validated reading materials, determining miscues, speed, and comprehension skills in both oral and silent reading through the implementation of the *Basa Baya Lahat* (Reading Brigade) program. The sets, as mentioned above, of data gathered through the tests were noted, analyzed, and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools.

Table 5 shows the results of the administered post-reading test after implementing the *Basa Baya Lahat* (Reading Brigade) program using the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach. This study revealed that the eight participants from all grade levels had improved their reading level from "frustration level" to "instructional level," where they met the required rating of 90% to 95%.

Based on the administered post-test, it was revealed that although they were still committing errors on the miscues analysis, namely, mispronunciation of words, omission of letters or words, insertion of letters or words, and substitution of letters or words, the percentage of the miscues had already lessened. In addition, there were fewer errors compared with the results before the program implementation. Moreover, the activities, worksheets, and approach with reading materials employed on the 15-day *Basa Baya Lahat* increased their reading level while lessening their

miscues. Teaching basic skills in alphabetic principle, showing the relationship between sounds and letters, greatly helped the students in word acquisition.

Table 5. *Post-Reading Test Results in Oral Reading Determining Miscues and Speed using the Simplified PVC Reading Approach*

ORAL READING – MISCUES AND SPEED							
Student No.	Gradelevel	Passage Total Words	Miscues	Total Correct Read Wordsper minute	Rating	Word Reading Level	
1	Grade 7	199	16	183	37	91.9 %	Instructional level
2	Grade 7	199	13	186	44	93.5 %	Instructional level
3	Grade 7	199	14	185	38	93%	Instructional level
4	Grade 7	199	13	186	31	93.5 %	Instructional level
5	Grade 7	199	10	189	63	95%	Instructional level
6	Grade 8	199	11	188	51	94.5 %	Instructional level
7	Grade 8	199	17	182	29	91.5 %	Instructional level
8	Grade 9	199	20	179	36	90%	Instructional level

This supports the research study of Ates (2013), when they revealed that there was an improvement in the student's word recognition accuracy, and the student's improvement was toward a higher reading level. Additionally, there was a decrease in the student's reading mistakes. Repeated reading interventions and feedback provided to the student after each reading performance positively impacted the student's reading fluency.

Another report from the National Reading Panel (2000) indicates that the highest student affects result when explicit, systematic instruction must provide both foundation skills. This includes phonological awareness and phonics, as well as higher-level reading tasks, such as fluency, with increased attention to word meaning and understanding of the text. With this, the research infers that the 15-day enhancement program using Simplified PVC has a significant impact on helping struggling readers.

Table 5.1 shows the results of the administered post-test in reading comprehension in oral reading using the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach and after

the implementation of the *Basa Baya Lahat* program. The researcher prepared and asked the participants to read aloud and answer the test, which included two passages followed by comprehension questions.

Based on the data collected, four out of the eight participants increased and progressed from "frustration level" to "independent level." These students were from grades 7 and 8 and met the required rating of 80–100%. While four out of eight participants increased and progressed on their current level from "frustration level" to "instructional level" as they met the required rating of 59–79%.

Table 5.1. *Post- Reading Test Results in Reading Comprehension Skills through Oral Reading using the Simplified PVC reading Approach*

Student No.	Grade Level	Passage 1		Passage 2		Total Score	Rating	Reading Level
		Score	No. of Questions	Score	No. of Questions			
1	Grade 7	8	10	8	10	16	80%	Independent Level
2	Grade 7	9	10	7	10	16	80%	Independent Level
3	Grade 7	8	10	8	10	16	80%	Instructional Level
4	Grade 7	10	10	8	10	15	75%	Instructional Level
5	Grade 7	10	10	8	10	18	90%	Independent Level
6	Grade 8	10	10	8	10	18	90%	Independent level
7	Grade 8	7	10	8	10	15	75%	Instructional level
8	Grade 9	7	10	7	10	14	70%	Instructional level

The results indicate that the Simplified PVC Reading approach helped the struggling readers comprehend the texts. Since the focus is to increase the reading level through comprehension skills of struggling readers, the provided reading material was effective as an instructional aid. The activities included a variety of passages focused on enhancing comprehension skills by noting details, getting the main idea, predicting outcomes or inferences, sequencing, and cause and effect, which significantly boosted their knowledge and confidence in reading, as also seen during the implementation of the enhancement program. Furthermore, it can be seen in the lesson or the reading text that they were related to the learners' interests and familiar to them since they were able to comprehend them somehow. It was observed that immediate feedback and monitoring of the students were factors in increasing their reading skills.

Teachers believe that reading aloud could enable students to develop meanings and make connections between ideas and experiences across texts. Reading aloud to students allowed them to hear the instructor exhibit reading fluency and expression. Moreover, asking students to read aloud to the class allows for a rapid and straightforward evaluation of their comprehension. It is vital to ask learners follow-up questions to assess their level of comprehension.

Table 5.2 shows the results of the oral reading comprehension post-test given after implementing the *Basa Baya Lahat* Program. The researcher made the test and asked the participants to read the two passages and answer the comprehension questions in silence.

Based on the gathered data, four out of eight participants increased and progressed on their current reading level from "frustration level" to "independent level". There were three from grade 7 and one from grade 8, who had met the required rating of 80–100%. While four out of eight participants— two students from grade 7, one from grade 8, and one from grade 9—increased and progressed on their current level from "frustration level" to "instructional level" as they met the required rating of 59–79%.

Table 5.2. *Post- Reading Test Results in Reading Comprehension Skills through Silent Reading using the Simplified PVC Reading Approach*

Student No.	Grade level	Passage 1		Passage 2		Total Score	Rating	Reading Level
		Score	No. of Questions	Score	No. of Questions			
1	Grade 7	9	10	8	10	17	85%	Independent level
2	Grade 7	8	10	8	10	16	80%	Independent level
3	Grade 7	10	10	8	10	15	75%	Instructional level
4	Grade 7	10	10	8	10	15	75%	Instructional level
5	Grade 7	9	10	9	10	18	90%	Independent Level
6	Grade 8	10	10	8	10	17	85%	Independent level
7	Grade 8	8	10	7	10	15	75%	Instructional level
8	Grade 9	7	10	7	10	14	70%	Instructional level

Therefore, the researcher can infer that the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach and materials have a

significant impact on increasing and progressing the reading skills development of the identified struggling readers.

Significant Improvement and Development of the Reading Skills through the Proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach

To see the significant improvement in the struggling readers' reading level after using the Simplified PVC Reading Approach, one-sample t-test was used.

Table 6 shows the results of a post-test in oral reading determining miscues and speed using the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach as reading material. This study reveals that the eight participants got a mean score of 92.863 in oral reading, determining miscues, and speed.

Table 6. Results of the Mean Determining Miscues and Speed

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Miscues and Speed	8	92.863	1.6501	.5834

This study reveals that the eight participants' reading levels in oral reading, determining miscues and speed, have significantly increased and improved. Moreover, this study means that the proposed approach and materials effectively developed the participants' word recognition.

Table 6.1 shows that the computed significant value for the mean difference of the two post-reading test results in oral reading through word recognition determining miscues and speed is 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05 or even 0.001 ($p < 0.001$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there was a statistically significant improvement in word recognition using the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach as a teaching aid for the reading skill development of struggling readers.

Table 6.1. Results of the Significant Improvement on Oral Comprehension Reading determining Miscues and Speed

	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Confidence Interval of the Difference		Verbal Interpretation
					Lower	Upper	
Miscues and Speed	9.329	7	.000	5.4425	4.063	6.822	Significant

Test Value = 87.42

Table 6.2 shows the result of the post-test in oral reading determining comprehension skills through oral reading using the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach and contextualized reading materials as an instructional aid. This study reveals that the eight participants got a mean score of 80.00 in comprehension skills through oral reading.

Table 6.2. Results of the Mean Determining Oral Reading Comprehension

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Oral reading comprehension	8	80.00	7.071	2.500

This indicates that the participant's score was higher than the previous post-test after implementing the Basa Baya Lahat program. Additionally, their reading level increased and improved in terms of comprehension skills in oral reading. As a result, the proposed reading strategy inevitably improved the students' reading abilities.

Table 6.3. Post-test Results Determining the Significant Improvement in Oral Comprehension Skills Reading

	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Confidence Interval of the Difference		Verbal Interpretation
					Lower	Upper	
Oral Reading Comprehension	8.584	7	.000	21.460	15.55	27.37	Significant

Test Value = 58.54

Table 6.3 shows that the computed significant value for the mean difference between the two post-reading test results determining the comprehension skills through oral reading is 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05 or even 0.001 ($p < 0.001$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there was a statistically significant improvement using the

proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach as a teaching aid for the reading skill development of struggling readers.

Table 6.4 shows the post-test result in oral reading for determining comprehension skills through silent reading using the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach with contextualized reading material. This study shows that the eight participants had a mean difference of 79.38 in comprehension skills when they read silently.

Table 6.4. Results of the Mean Determining the Silent Comprehension Skills Reading

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Silent Reading Comprehension	8	79.38	6.781	2.397

This study indicates that the eight participants have significantly increased and improved their reading performances. Moreover, the proposed approach and the contextualized reading materials improved their comprehension skills through silent reading.

Table 6.5 shows that the computed significant value for the mean difference of the two post-reading test results determining the comprehension skills through silent reading is 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05 or even 0.001 ($p < 0.001$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there was a statistically significant improvement in word recognition using the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach as a teaching aid for the skill development of struggling readers.

Table 6.5. Post test Results determining the Significant Improvement on Silent Comprehension Reading

	T	nr	Sig. (2-tailed)	Test Value = 56.55			Verbal Interpretation
				Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval Lower	95% Confidence Interval Upper	
Silent Reading Comprehension	9.521	7	.000	22.825	17.16	28.49	Significant

These findings are consistent with the study conducted by Akjol et al., (2014), which found that after the study, the participants' word recognition and silent and oral reading comprehension abilities improved.

To improve the reading skills of students with reading difficulties, constructing an appropriate reading environment and implementing enrichment reading programs could be effective.

Along with this, a few studies have also revealed the effectiveness of different programs. Research findings demonstrate the effectiveness of reading programs implemented in developing nations (Friedlander & Goldenberg, 2016). Like reading programs in developed nations, most programs aim to increase reading frequency, enhance reading education, or both. For instance, research revealed that effective reading instruction and book distribution had a favorable influence on the reading achievement of Rwandan pupils. Abeberese et al. (2014) discovered similar outcomes when well-trained teachers and sufficient reading materials need to provide to Filipino pupils. These findings are crucial for developing nations, as data indicates that poor children are susceptible to developmental delays due to reading difficulties.

The Implication of the Proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach through the Basa Baya Lahat Program (Reading Brigade) to the Reading Skills Development of the Struggling Readers

Based from the results of the administered post-test, this study implies that the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach has significant improvement to the reading skills development of struggling readers through the 15-day implementation of the Basa Baya Lahat (Reading Brigade) program.

With these findings, here are the following implications:

1. The study's findings reveal that the proposed reading approach, along with validated reading materials, provided a significant positive effect on the improvement of reading skill development as students increased their reading level in terms of word recognition and comprehension skills in both oral and silent reading.
2. This study implies that the first step to improving students' reading skills is to put more emphasis on teaching phonological awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension.
3. This study implies there is still time for intervention for struggling adolescent readers if they receive appropriate, focused, and effective reading instruction.
4. It also implies that the progression of contextualizing reading materials should continue to assist struggling readers through various theories, strategies, and approaches.
5. This study further implies that the teacher must

assess the learner's reading behavior. As per observations made before the enhancement reading program's implementation, some participants read word-for-word, lacked expression, had barely audible voices, and ignored punctuation marks.

With this, it was brought to the attention of the teacher that the learners need to improve not only their miscues in word recognition and comprehension but also how to become effective readers. That is why the researcher proposed this simplified PVC reading approach, which is an excellent way to get beginning readers who are doing well to become independent readers since the materials use different activities. The learner showed improvement from time to time during the discussion. The 15-day skill enhancement program helps the students gradually improve their skills, as shown by their daily activity scores and the teacher's encouragement and immediate feedback.

In addition, recent reviews have explored the effectiveness of approaches to enhance reading results for older adolescents with persistent reading issues in grades 4–12. According to Edmonds et al. (2009), supported by Kamil et al. (2008), explicit instruction in word study strategies to decode words, word meanings, and strategies for determining the meanings of unknown words, as well as training in comprehension strategy, is linked to positive reading outcomes for older students.

Similarly, Flores (2009) underlines that reading is one of the essential skills with the ability to speak effectively and write in various forms and for various purposes; reading competency can open avenues for different learning opportunities.

Therefore, the study's findings imply that the continuous development of theories, strategies, and approaches can help address learners' growing reading deficiencies over time and thus develop their reading skills in the long run.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the proposed Simplified PVC Reading Approach with contextualized reading materials, when put into practice through the 15-day Basa Lahat (Reading Brigade) program, significantly improved the reading skills of eight struggling readers at Argao National High School. This study has shown the post-test scores using one sample t-test and the PHIL-IRI tool results. Hence, the research alternative hypothesis is *valid and accepted*.

In addition, the findings further shows that the *Basa Baya Lahat* program could adopt other suggested reading techniques. This study can present a teaching strategy for struggling readers following the program so that the students' reading development could be continuously monitored. This study also highlighted the significance of assessment and feedback for continued monitoring the student's reading levels.

This study helps pave the way and create the opportunity to design and craft an appropriate and effective approach to teaching reading. This proposed reading technique and the strategy adopted to determine its impacts on the development of the reading skills of struggling readers enhanced the students' word recognition and comprehension abilities. As a whole, the output of this study can serve as the basis for continuing and developing this functional reading program and intensifying it through enhancement programs and interventions.

Assessing the effects of the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach with suggested reading materials on the reading skills development of struggling readers is significantly required for the continued creation and development of reading approaches and materials for use in various reading enhancement programs. Furthermore, all stakeholders must work together to benefit the student's learning process.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the researcher recommends the following:

1. To the Department of Education

1.1. The researcher hopes that the proposed Simplified PVC reading approach will be considered and used as a teaching method to help struggling readers improve their reading performance as part of an enhancement or remediation program.

1.2. School administrators can provide funds to print the materials as a working tool and distribute them in every school to improve the reading performance of struggling readers through a program like the Basa Baya Lahat program.

2. To Teachers

2.1. The researcher believes that this research study will provide knowledge and awareness about the student's current problem in their reading ability that requires an immediate solution on how to diagnose the reading problem.

2.2. This study may educate teachers on prioritizing and budgeting their time to scaffold and assist struggling readers through various intervention programs. Moreover, they may strengthen their delivery of instruction by conducting remedial

teaching or follow-up sessions on reading whenever necessary.

3. To Students

3.1. The researcher believes this can be used as reading material or a reference to help improve their reading skills, such as word recognition, vocabulary, and comprehension.

3.2. They will find interest, encouragement, and confidence as they read the different activities in the reading materials.

4. To Future Researchers

4.1. The researcher wishes that this study will be a reference for future research endeavors with different objectives, samples, and methodologies about reading.

4.2. They may need to do intensive research with a larger sample size of participants to prove further the effectiveness of the proposed simplified PVC reading approach.

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